

Ethical Implications of Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT: The technological progress of the first decades of the 21st century has an unprecedented pace, changing various aspects of our lives. The Fourth and Fifth Industrial Revolutions fueled transformations that impact political systems, economic processes, social structures, and the environment that shields the existence of the human race. The latest innovations are influencing new developments in healthcare and education as well. The technological landscape is shaped today by the emergence of a new capability of computational systems, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the tools it enables. The main goal of this paper is to formulate some preliminary conclusions regarding the impact of AI on higher education across various regions of the globe. The main focus of our endeavor is to present some ethical consequences of the interaction between the education system and new technologies. Both risks and opportunities are highlighted, with elements such as accessibility, assistive technology, transparency, academic integrity, or intellectual property examined through a qualitative methodological approach.

KEYWORDS: higher education, Artificial Intelligence (AI), academic integrity, ethics, equity, large language models (LLMs)

1. Introduction

In 2016, the German economist, engineer, and founder of the World Economic Forum (WEF), Klaus Schwab, published a highly cited and debated book titled *The Fourth Industrial Revolution* (Schwab, 2016). Schwab argued that industrial capitalism is being reshaped by the rhythm of technological advancement; the latest evolutions boosted the importance of robotics in several fields, paved the way for handling human genes in innovative ways, and created conditions for building augmented social realities. The concept of metaverse, which refers to a three-dimensional online environment, is seen by several academics as a key component of the lives of future generations (Ritterbusch & Teichmann, 2023).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the pillars of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which nowadays seems to be paving the way for its successor, the Fifth Industrial Revolution. The Fifth Industrial Revolution further enhances the importance of robotics, revolutionizing medical instruments or the energetic domain (Alok, 2025). This latest stage of industrial development is creating opportunities for building a more prosperous and harmonious future, but is also bringing risks regarding the phenomenon of alienation that affects numerous individuals or regarding the stability of the ethical principles that should govern the existence of our communities. Principles such as honesty, integrity, respect, responsibility, environmental consciousness, or transparency can be endangered by the inappropriate utilization of technological tools that currently are enthusiastically embraced by a large number of people.

As highlighted above, AI is an essential factor for all these processes. The late US (United States) diplomat and political scientist Henry Kissinger, who served as Secretary of State between 1973 and 1977, stated that AI applications based on large language models like ChatGPT, are opening extraordinary possibilities for progress, but at the same time, if they are not properly handled, an existential threat to humanity could emerge (Kissinger et al., 2023). A similar warning was issued more recently by Pope Leo XIV, who argued that AI can generate significant challenges to human dignity, to the stability of labor markets, or even to equity and social justice (Matei, 2025).

AI could dismantle a large number of jobs in the not-so-distant future. While more optimistic analyses anticipate that AI could produce between 20 and 50 million jobs like trainer, data analyst, or policy specialist by 2030 (Farrell, n.d.), others are worried that technological developments might increase the level of unemployment worldwide. For instance, it is obvious that the expansion of AI tools in the job market may create difficulties for those employees with limited digital skills, with the largest percentage of vulnerable workers being among older generations (Stelmach, 2025).

The impact of AI on education is already substantial, and normally it will only increase in the following years. The higher education system is even more

susceptible to being influenced, given that AI may create worrisome problems regarding academic integrity, authorship, or the trust in the relationship between scholars and their disciples. Therefore, if we bring universities under the lens of our analysis, we discover that the discussion has far more facets than the standard question marks regarding the stability of the jobs held by teachers or researchers.

We aim through this research to highlight the current and potential implications of the use of AI tools in higher education. The ethical aspect is central for our paper, but the analysis is not limited to elements linked to it. We do not intend to build a case study on a particular higher education system, our intention is to formulating preliminary conclusions that are relevant regardless of the geographical region in which a university operates. Although it might seem excessively ambitious, this kind of approach is encouraged by the fact that the internationalization of higher education fully integrated the main characteristics of globalization in this field as well. Nevertheless, it must be emphasized that most of the examples we observed are offered by universities from Europe or North America, which means that some of our arguments have a higher relevance in the Global North than in the Global South.

Some of the topics discussed in our study are the following: personalized learning, open educational resources, the influence of technology on the efficiency of scholars, intellectual property and plagiarism, the perpetuation of biases in higher education through AI tools, transparency, equity, and the social consequences of the new paradigm that appears in higher education.

2. Methodology

Our study is built by using qualitative methodological tools. The research adopts a desk review methodology, collecting and evaluating information from secondary sources. We review already available data, academic literature, and several other reports and analyses (think tank reports, NGO publications, etc.). The research design is exploratory, with the goal of mapping existing knowledge in order to develop relevant insights for the subject we focus on. Although the topic of the paper emerged quite recently, extensive information about it already exists in academia and in the public space. All the sources we consulted are written in English, although not all of them concern English-speaking countries. Moreover, all but one of the sources are published after 2023, so it can be stated that both recency and relevance are ensured. We reviewed only sources that are characterized by transparency and provide evidence useful for developing our study. Such a qualitative methodological approach also has limitations, depending on the availability and quality of existing literature. Nevertheless, it can build a strong foundation for further research or policy development.

3. The role of human educators in the AI era: potential benefits and threats

The new technological tools create possibilities for personalizing the educational process in ways that were almost impossible to reach a few decades ago. Platforms managed by AI can create or identify material adapted to the needs of a student and can help generate adequate feedback (Bozkurt, 2023). Adapting the teaching to the specific needs and traits of a student can be beneficial for his evolution. However, it is often underlined that AI can make the students over-rely on the tools that it provides; many might easily conclude that instruments like ChatGPT can replace the formal or informal interaction with professors (Medina, 2024). On the other hand, teachers might fall into the exact same trap: they might consider that the platforms have the best understanding of the students' needs and that they can simply deliver to them the outcomes of the activity of large language models. Reducing genuine human contact in the educational act is not only detrimental to the efficiency of teaching but also abhorrent from an ethical point of view.

Despite these ethical concerns, it is clear that, if properly used, AI tools can help teachers to better organize their schedules, and manage routine activities more efficiently. These can help them be more effective in their tasks; planning lessons, upgrading the curriculum, or completing paperwork can become much less stressful with the help of new technologies (Euclea Editorial Team, 2025). Nevertheless, if the professor has a twisted understanding of how AI can assist him in his work, negative ethical consequences can take shape in these cases as well. Essential for the integrity of the process is to help teachers understand that large language models can be useful instruments, not authority figures that provide trustworthy directions for the manner in which one should build his/her career.

Assistive technology driven by AI can be useful not only in routine situations but also in special cases, having the capability of making higher education more equitable. For instance, students or scholars with different disabilities can normally perform educational activities with the help of smart assisting devices (Every Learner Everywhere, 2025). For example, speech-to-text programs can facilitate the integration into the educational environment of those who otherwise might have felt excluded or sabotaged; such instruments can have a profound impact on their mental health as well. In the case of neurodivergent students, an AI planning assistant can have a high utility. Vanderbilt University in Nashville, Tennessee, USA, has already implemented such an instrument (Miller, 2023).

In the following years, it could become extremely important for higher education that AI applications have the ability to create textbooks or translate different texts in virtually any language needed. Open Educational Resources (OER) could witness a spectacular quantitative increase, which theoretically can improve the results of both students and teachers. The reliability of this process might be ensured by organizing it in accordance with curriculum guidelines (Bozkurt, 2023). However, the new textbooks, worksheets, or translations should

be carefully reviewed by human educators; otherwise, it will be impossible to eliminate the risk of doubling the mentioned quantitative increase with a qualitative slump. A study based on educators from Austria, Germany, and Switzerland highlighted the importance of ensuring that any OER meets the qualitative standards necessary for an authentic and efficient educational process (Rampelt et al., 2025). Moreover, a potential peril of involving AI programs in generating OERs involves harming intellectual property. More on this topic will be discussed in the following section.

The main lesson that can be learned from the information exposed above is that AI can be extremely useful in higher education, but it cannot replace, not even partly, the human educator. The creativity, moral sense, and sound judgment of a professor are unachievable and will remain so at least for the foreseeable future for AI programs. If a teacher cedes the main responsibilities of his role to an artificial entity, it betrays the ethical core of the mission he accepted. A human educator is gifted with genuine empathy and can deliver a subtle perspective on the importance of critical thinking that is unobtainable for a large language model. However, by presenting the limits of AI, we do not intend to underestimate its ability to generate positive outcomes. AI literacy has already become an essential part of a didactic career (Medina, 2024).

4. Intellectual property and authorship

We briefly previously discussed the AI's capability of creating new OERs. It is important to specify that large language models cannot hold copyright, given that they cannot take responsibility for the content they produce, so they cannot be listed as authors. The Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), a non-governmental organization (NGO) founded in the United Kingdom (UK) in 1997, recently stated not only that tools like ChatGPT cannot be listed as co-authors but also that the use of such programs must be disclosed (Weinberg, 2023). A similar recommendation was issued by the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE, 2025, p. 3). Indeed, it is of paramount importance for higher education systems and for their ethical foundations that both students and teachers specify if and how they use AI in their activities. Otherwise, a climate of distrust can gradually impose itself in universities all over the globe.

It is the responsibility of human educators to verify and adapt AI-generated content, correcting potential errors regarding the paternity of some of the information or ideas provided. Both the accuracy and the originality of the data must be thoroughly vetted by an academic that uses an AI tool. Only such conduct can significantly reduce the chances of harming someone's intellectual property. The appropriate specification of sources must always be the duty of the author; he must always keep in mind that his own authorship will be devalued if such issues

are treated in a superficial manner. The lack of transparency regarding AI can also be harmful to ethics in higher education.

Addressing the negative effects of the utilization of AI in academics cannot be left exclusively to the honesty and best intentions of the students or teachers. A recent global survey shows that already 86% of students are using large language models (Digital Education Council, 2024). It is easily understandable that, given the scale of the practice, ethical barriers might be often crossed. Teachers can also engage in unethical acts that involve AI platforms. For instance, a student from Northeastern University in Boston, Massachusetts, USA, issued a complaint regarding the hypocritical feedback given to her and her colleagues by a teacher who used ChatGPT and demanded the repayment of her tuition fee (Hill, 2025). Such cases could be prevented (through avoiding ChatGPT or disclosing its use) if the availability of AI detection tools would increase.

5. Academic integrity and assessment

Another study conducted on more than 1,000 US students in 2023 revealed that 89% of them used ChatGPT for writing their homework. The survey also interviewed more than 100 college educators. 82% were aware of the existence of ChatGPT, and 72% of them were extremely concerned regarding the possibility of students cheating by using the application (Ward, 2023). This data underlines the risks that, in certain conditions, AI can pose to academic integrity. Moreover, one of the main outcomes of this new environment can be that more and more graduates will fill the labor market while being severely underprepared for the jobs they will be taking on (Medina, 2024).

As highlighted above, not even those in teaching positions are fully immune to using AI in a dishonest way. Therefore, the already mentioned AI detection tools are of paramount importance. However, creating and valorizing them is not just a question of will, but also one of resources, infrastructure, and adaptability. As the Fifth Industrial Revolution imposes itself on a global scale, the rhythm of developing new technological instruments increases, making it more difficult for potential detection programs to be 100% efficient. So far, some programs have shown their limits. For instance, most of these tools are trained with data written by native English speakers. Therefore, it is quite likely that at least some of them will incorrectly label as AI-generated original text written by those who speak English as a foreign language. The analysis of 91 essays from a Chinese forum, written by people who have English as a second language, revealed that the false-positive rate was higher than 60%, while the papers written by native English speakers were accurately diagnosed (Liang et al., 2023).

Given that, at least for now, AI detection tools are not entirely trustworthy, the main adjustment that professors can make in order to neutralize the dangers posed by AI is linked to the assessment process. If the students are evaluated in a

manner that circumvents the possibility of using programs like ChatGPT, the ethical pillars of higher education will emerge unshaken: „In the age of generative AI, authentic assessment is more important than ever. Injecting personal perspectives, critical thinking, and self-reflection in a way that appears genuine is much more difficult for generative AI technologies than it is for humans.” (White, 2023) On one hand, indeed the particularities of the tasks given to the students can render useless the recourse to large language models. On the other hand, even more efficient could be a return to classical oral evaluations. An open and multifaceted discussion between a student who perhaps used AI in order to prepare for the exam and the teacher can secure the outcome of having no gap between the student's abilities and his academic results. In this entire process, the starting point of any pedagogical strategy should be that of providing clear guidelines. The students must know precisely what is allowed and what is forbidden when it comes to AI.

6. Transparency, trust, and potential biases

As previously mentioned, an educator cannot require honesty or dedication from students if they are not predictable in their activities or if they do not respect the rules they impose. For the proper functioning of the educational process, it is essential that transparency regarding the limits in the use of AI programs is doubled by reasonability. It would be absurd for a teacher to expect that the students will renounce the use of ChatGPT or other similar applications just because a formal rule requires it. One of the main lessons of the Fifth Industrial Revolution is that AI is here to stay. Our lives and those of future generations will take place under the specter of this impressive technological innovation. Therefore, if educators desire to have transparency as a foundation for a relationship with students based on trust, they have to accept this new reality and replace outright animosity towards AI with clearly delimiting what is acceptable and what is unethical in students' interactions with large language models.

Building trust in higher education concerning the use of AI is a difficult mission if teachers and students do not share a common understanding of how AI programs function, what their strengths are, and that their abilities are not borderless, with AI being fallible just as human beings are. Therefore, training or workshops on this topic are extremely important; every university should make it a priority to ensure that both its students and its professors are participating in such activities. It is normal for people, regardless of age, to be impressed by the continually progressing technological landscape of the 21st century. However, this state of awe can easily lead to over-trusting the tools that are truly valuable if they are properly handled by humans. An AI application cannot be recognized as an authority in any scientific field; its main ability is to replicate human language and compile information, not to generate judgments that ought to be accepted without

any questioning. AI is extremely efficient in pattern recognition but, at least for now, is unable to reason on its own: „AI can form conclusions that we can test. But, as weird as it is to think about, this isn't the core of reasoning, it's just a really great benefit. Reasoning isn't about the conclusion we reach, but the process our thinking goes through to reach that conclusion (...) Contrary to popular opinion, reasoning isn't void of emotion either. Far too many people view reasoning through a prism of logic, math, and other emotionless forms of processing. This, I believe, is incorrect. To begin with, there's never been a convincing argument that reasoning should be void of emotion. We cannot understand anything by ignoring and/or trying to remove our emotions from learning. The evidence for this argument is what apathy does to learning” (Maille, 2023).

The use of pattern recognition predisposes AI applications to replicate human biases that are heavily rooted in different cultural environments. Inadvertently (as we mentioned that AI cannot reason), large language models can perpetuate stereotypes that can be harmful in one way or another. For instance, when an AI program was required to present an example of a remarkable STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) student, it chose an Asian-named student, Priya (Kannan, 2024). Perpetuating such stereotypes can affect the sense of belonging or the self-image of both Asian students who struggle with some courses and of students with a different racial or cultural background. This adds another layer to the discussion about the ethical implications of the use of AI in higher education, one that touches on the topic of equitability.

7. Equity and accessibility

AI programs can have an important role in improving accessibility to higher education. Nevertheless, some aspects of the proliferation of such programs in the educational process were not discussed yet in our paper. We highlighted that educators must provide clear guidelines concerning what is allowed and what is unethical in the interaction between a student and an AI application. But can all students have access to such applications? We must take into account that several AI learning platforms are commercially licensed. Therefore, students who want to use them (or at least their premium version) have to pay fees that can reach considerable amounts. Obviously, this has a negative impact on a system that, in many countries, still has serious issues regarding the fairness of access and evolution. In these cases, excellence can be conditioned by the financial resources of a student or his family. Therefore, instead of helping to create bonds in student communities, AI can contribute to widening already existing gaps (Wargo & Anderson, 2024).

Once again, we must emphasize that it is important for universities to step up and make the proper decisions to maintain the ethical foundation of the educational process. Ensuring access to AI programs for students, combined with

providing clear guidelines for utilizing them, can prevent a negative impact on the principle of equal opportunities. On the other hand, in some cases, this could increase the financial burden of a higher education institution. Therefore, the coordination between universities and the government is extremely important. Strategic planning regarding the role and the use of AI must take place at multiple levels, with central and local authorities having the capabilities to assist universities in managing such a volatile environment.

The complexity of this topic is reflected by another element. Not only that, paying the fees for AI applications might enable the students who are ignoring guidelines to cheat, but it also can have a negative impact on the environment. At least for now, the functioning of large language models requires impressive amounts of energy. Therefore, the more we use AI, the more we contribute to the sabotaging of the efforts to neutralize climate change. Until our energetic systems depend mainly on green sources or AI becomes more efficient with less energy, this will be a key part of the ethical dilemma that surrounds the relationship between AI and higher education. Some tools might bring extraordinary advantages from an economic or educational point of view, but we must also keep an eye on their overall impact on the well-being of the human race before reaching definitive conclusions regarding their utility.

8. Conclusions

Only disasters of apocalyptic proportions could stop the unprecedented pace of technological progress that characterizes the 21st century. Of course, although some effects of globalization are almost impossible to reverse, differences between regions in this regard might remain or appear. Nevertheless, overall, we can state that AI programs will continue to have a growing importance in our lives. Obviously, this applies to higher education as well.

The ethical implications of this new landscape are multifaceted. Throughout developing our research, we determined that the principles of fairness or compassion can be enhanced through properly using the new tools. On the other hand, they can provide various possibilities for undermining key elements of the academic environment, like fairness or integrity. Students or even teachers can disrespect their activity by delegating some of their responsibilities to large language models that are unable to reason or to empathize. Moreover, AI can be used both to boost and to reduce transparency in universities. Another aspect worth underlining is that regardless of the manner in which these programs are used, their functioning requires large amounts of energy, which can obviously be harmful for the environment. All the potential negative impacts can be avoided or mitigated only if those who are involved in higher education take a proactive approach. Maintaining the ethical foundation of academia will be difficult if

managers or other involved parties will be passive in front of the new waves of technological innovation.

AI platforms can be extremely useful in increasing accessibility in universities and in assisting teachers, but they cannot replace them. Both students and educators commit a grave error if they see AI platforms as authority figures in scientific fields. Large language models can provide information and can suggest possible interpretations but cannot reason on their own. Anything that resulted from a conversation with ChatGPT or similar instruments must be double-checked. Moreover, teachers must provide students with clear guidelines regarding the use of AI, given that discouraging them from using it is doomed to fail. On the other hand, professors might reduce the role of AI in the educational process if they make proper adjustments concerning the evaluation of the students.

AI platforms can easily reproduce biases or the erroneous judgments that characterize human thinking. One of the main differences between ChatGPT and a teacher is that the former definitely lacks emotion or empathy. Therefore, however well trained it is, it might easily slide towards delivering cynical conclusions instead of nuanced perspectives. For instance, AI might prioritize economic efficiency or the goal of fitting students to the requirements of the job market instead of helping them become responsible citizens and human beings who genuinely care for the communities they live in and for the environment.

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